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Survey of *mycotoxins* in Kilishi (dried meat) produced and sold at Sokoto and Katsina states local government areas, Nigeria

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This study was carried out to determine the occurrence of fungi in already processed and ready-to-eat Kilishi sold in some local government of Sokoto and Katsina States. The fungal population was isolated, characterized and identified. The fungi isolated were identified to include *Aspergillus niger*, *Aspergillus flavus*, *Aspergillus fumigatus* and *Candida albicans*. The present work indicated that the examined dried meats were contaminated with several moulds especially of the genus *Aspergillus*. Many of these moulds are capable of producing mycotoxin such as aflatoxins, ochratoxin and fumonisins. These findings indicate that there may be a risk of human exposure to mycotoxins through the consumption of the dried meat. Strict hygienic measures must be applied during the processing and storage of the meat samples and calls for concerted efforts on the part of relevant authorities to check the trend, since it is a public health challenge.

Key words: - *Aspergillus spp*, *Katsina*, *Sokoto*, *Candida albicans*, *Mycotoxins*, *Survey*

INTRODUCTION

Mycotoxins are low molecular weight secondary metabolites produced by filamentous microfungi that are capable of causing disease and death in humans and animals (D'mello and Macdonald, 1998; Bennett, 1987). Depending on the definition used, and recognizing that most fungal toxins occur in families of chemically related metabolites, some 300-400 compounds are now recognized as mycotoxins of which approximately a dozen groups receive attention as threat to human and animal health (Cole and Cox, 1981). Mycotoxin exposure is more likely to occur in parts of the world where poor

methods of food handling and storage are common, where malnutrition is a problem, where few regulations exist to protect exposed population (Barrett, 2000).

The proliferation of various fungi in agricultural products leads to reduction in yield and quality with significant economic losses (Bankole, 1994). Mycotoxins are produced by some of the specific strains of filamentous fungi belonging to species of the genera *Aspergillus*, *Penicillium*, and *Fusarium* that invade crops at the field level and may grow on foods during storage under favourable conditions (temperature, moisture, water activity and relative humidity). The principal classes of mycotoxins include metabolites of *A. flavus*, and *A. parasiticus*. Aflatoxin BI (AFBI) is the most potent hepatocarcinogenic substance known, which has been

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recently proven to be genotoxic. Others are zearalenone (ZEA), trichotecenes, deoxynivalenol (DON), fumonisins (OTA) and ergot alkaloids (Whitlow, *et al.*, 2000).

Fungi normally grow between 10 – 40°C over a pH range of 4-8 and at water activity (*aw*) levels above 0.70 (Lacey, 1991). The nature and quantity of mycotoxin produced is entirely influenced by interactions of several factors; types of substrate, moisture content, available nutrition, temperature, humidity in the surrounding environment, maturity of the fungal colony, co-occurrence with other fungi, competition from other micro-organisms, stress factors, physical damage of the substrate due to insect activity and other associated factors (Anonymous, 1983; Coulombe, 1993; Hendry and Cole, 1993; Viquez, *et al.*, 1994; Rao, 2001).

Kilishi which is a traditional sun-dried Nigerian and Sahelian African meat product whose origin is lost in antiquity, was developed by early Hausa and Fulani tribesmen. 'Kilishi' is a Hausa word, which refers to cattle, sheep or goat meat that is processed by slicing, sun drying, application of slurry of spices and roasting in a glowing fire (Ipinjoli *et al.*, 2005). As a ready to eat and convenient meat product, Kilishi has excellent shelf life at room temperature (Igene *et al.*, 1990). The traditional way of Kilishi production involves trimming tendons and fat, and slicing fresh meat to obtain the sheets (Musonge and Njolai, 1994). Kilishi is a tropical intramuscular (IM) meat product prepared essentially from ray thin beat slices of 2mm thickness infused in slurry of defatted groundnut paste and spices, and sundried (Ogunsola and Omojola, 2008). Mycotoxin exposure is more likely to occur in parts of the world where poor methods of food handling and storage are common, where malnutrition is a problem, and where few regulations exist to protect exposed populations. However, even in developed countries, specific groups may be vulnerable to mycotoxin (Barrett, 2000).

Aflatoxin contamination has been linked to increased mortality in farm animals and thus significantly lowers the value of grains as an animal feed and as an export commodity. When cows consume aflatoxin-contaminated feeds, they metabolically biotransform aflatoxin B₁ into a hydroxylated form called aflatoxin M₁ (Van Egmond, 1989). Mycotoxins occur, with varying severity, in agricultural products all around the world. The estimate usually given is that one quarter of the world crops are contaminated to some extent with mycotoxins (FAO, 2004). Mycotoxins can enter the food chain in the field, during storage, or at later points. Mycotoxin problems are exacerbated whenever shipping, handling, and storage practices are conducive to mold growth. The end result is that mycotoxins are commonly found in foods.

The economic consequences of mycotoxin contamination are profound. Crops with large amounts of mycotoxins often have to be destroyed. Alternatively, contaminated crops are sometimes diverted into animal feed. Giving contaminated feeds to susceptible animals

can lead to reduced growth rates, illness, and death. Moreover, animals consuming mycotoxin-contaminated feeds can produce meat and milk that contain toxic residues and biotransformation products. Thus, aflatoxins in cattle feed can be metabolized by cows into aflatoxin M₁, which is then secreted in milk (Van Egmond, 1989). Ochratoxin in pig feed can accumulate in porcine tissues (Rutqvist *et al.*, 1978). The ability to diagnose and verify mycotoxicoses is an important forensic aspect of the mycotoxin problem (Peterson, *et al.*, 2001). The Hausas refer to dried meat as kilishi which is usually made of beef and rarely from chicken, lamb or goat. It consists of spices, and mainly hawked in the Northern parts of Nigeria (Alonge and Hiko, 1981). Kilishi is mostly sold in streets by hawkers on the road side, bus stops, market places and areas or places of business attraction. Unfortunately, this delicacy is mostly processed and handled in an unhygienic manner as hawkers sometimes carry this meat in an open wide tray, exposed to flies and dusts. Most hawkers are illiterates; hence they do not have scientific ideas on food handling and environment (Frazier and Westhoff, 1991).

The processing of Kilishi which includes slices of meat; dried or smoked, seasoned with cocktail of ingredients and grilled or not on firewood, is fraught with a lot of challenges. Slicing and low technological quality of meat constitute the major technological constraints of kilishi manufacturing process (Ndih' Ndjouenkeu and Etoa, 2018). Previous scientific findings have documented *Salmonella* species, *Campylobacter* species, enterotoxigenic *Escherichia coli*, *Listeria monocytogenes*, *Clostridium botulinum*, *Yersinia enterocolitica*, *perfringens*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, and *Vibrio* species have been documented as pathogenic micro-organisms presenting the greatest risk with meat (Anon, 2004; USDA/ERS, 2003).

Nigeria had experience high recorded aflatoxin exposure levels in humans and has also reported the highest estimated number of cases of hepatocellular carcinoma (HCC-liver cancer) to aflatoxin in the whole world (Liu and Wu, 2010). Due to the insidious nature of mycotoxin production and the resulting disease state which made diagnosis of mycotoxicosis difficult, many cases of both human and animal mycotoxicoses have often not been reported in Nigeria. This suggests that little has been done on mycotoxicosis in Nigeria and there is paucity of information on mycotoxin in the country. Lack of awareness of the dangers posed by mycotoxin contamination of produce is a major factor responsible for its high incidence in Nigeria. Majority of farmers, produce and food handlers and/or processors are illiterate with virtually no knowledge of the implications of toxigenic mould growth. In Nigeria documentation of mycotoxin related human health problems is not extensive. However, the few literatures available show evidence of human mycotoxicoses and suspected mycotoxicoses (Ikeorah and Okoye, 2005). Kilishi is a product from beef

Figure 3.1 Typical kilishi production in Katsina State in the study area

which is being consumed locally and internationally. It is of high export value and has been having a lot of rejections in the export market because of food safety issues especially mycotoxins. The essence of this work is to assess the quality of kilishi especially on mycotoxin to ensure wholesomeness for local and international consumption or market.

The aim of the study is to determine the presence of *Aspergillus* species and aflatoxins in kilishi. The objectives of the study were; to isolate, identify and characterise *Aspergillus* species in kilishi in Katsina and Sokoto state, determine the occurrence of aflatoxins in kilishi, and Questionnaire to find the level of awareness on mycotoxins

MATERIALS AND METHOD

Study Area

The study is to be carried out in Katsina state in seven Local Government Areas (LGA) of the two states. Katsina state is located to the North West zone of the country and is bounded to the north by Niger Republic, to the west by Zamfara state, to the south by Kaduna state and to the east by Kano state. The annual temperature averages 26°C while the annual rainfall is averages 600mm. the rainy season is from May- September with the peak in July and August. It has an annual average temperature of 28°C with maximum day time temperature of 40°C. (Tsoho, 2007). The rainy season is from June- October. The mean annual rainfall is between 500-1,300mm and has two main seasons, the dry and wet season. Katsina state is located to the North West zone of the country and is bounded to the north by Niger Republic, to the west by

Zamfara state, to the south by Kaduna state and to the east by Kano state. The annual temperature averages 26°C while the annual rainfall is averages 600mm. the rainy season is from May- September with the peak in July and August.

Sample and Sampling

A total of 65 samples of kilishi was collected from the community markets and areas of production for analysis. The sample size was determined using standard deviation of 0.5, confidence level of 95% and confidence interval (margin of error) of +/-7.3%. The samples were collected and analyzed as such. Samples were collected randomly from the community markets and areas of production through the beef value chain

Processing of Kilishi Samples

The whole kilishi is to be measured and placed into Ziploc bags aseptically before freezing. Each sample will be macerated, homogenized and 1g sub sample is to be added to 90ml of methanol /distilled water (70:30vv) in a test tube and mixed for 10 minutes at room temperature (20-25°C) using a shaker (Trucses, 2000). The entire extract is filtered using a filter paper: 100ul of the filtrate is diluted with 600 ul distilled water, 50ul per well is to be employed and the washing procedure is done as written in the owner's manual (r-bio pharm, 2013). Absorbance will read within 30 minutes at 450nm.

Preparation of Culture Media and Identification of *Aspergillus* in Kilishi

Exactly 16g of rose Bengal Chloramphenicol agar a

selective media for growth of *Aspergillus* specie is added to 500ml distilled water and boil, and sterilized at 121^oC for 15 minutes. The mixture was be allowed to cool to about 50^oC after which chloramphenicol (100mg/L) will be added. Plates will be left to cool down and solidify.

Exactly 10g of kilishi is to be added into 90 ml of sterile distilled water and mixed thoroughly with stomacher. One drop of each mixture will be inoculated into labelled plates containing the selective media for the growth of *Aspergillus* species (Rosebengal chloramphenicol agar) and inoculated at room temperature for 72 hours. Thereafter, plates will be examined macroscopically for characteristic colonies of *Aspergillus* species: colony, colour and thermo tolerant (Giorni *et al.*, 2007) colonies will be counted and pictures was taken.

Microscopic Examination of Cultures

One to two drops of lactophenol cotton blue were placed on a clean glass slide. Using of sterilized platinum inoculating pin, a bit of the suspected fungal growth is to be pick from the medium and place on the slide. This is then teased out and covered with glass cover slip. This is press down slightly with the tip of the finger to expel any air bubble and further disintegrate the hypal growth to enhance observation. The slides will be observed under x 0 magnification of a light microscope. Microscopic characteristics of fungi such as hypae conidial heads and arrangements conidia was observed.

Determination of Aflatoxins in Kilishi using Enzyme Linked Immune Sorbent Assay

The enzyme linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) is to be carried out according to the methods by Radisson (r-Bio pharm, 2013). The reagents in the ELISA kit are adjusted to room temperature (25^oC) prior to test. The kilishi sample is to be macerated and mixed using mortar and pestle. One gram of the kilishi sample is to be place into a screw cap glass vial, 9ml of methanol /distilled water (70/30v/v) is to be add and mixed for ten minutes at room temperature (20 – 25^oC) using a shaker. The entire extract will be filtered using a filter paper and 100ul of filtrate will be diluted with 600ul distilled water. Prepared sample and 50ul of standard solution will be added to each well. Exactly 50ul of enzyme conjugate will be added in the 96 well ELISA. Fifty microliters of antibody solution will be added to each well and mixed gently by shaking the plate manually and incubated for 30 minutes at room temperature (20 – 25^oC).

The mixture was poured out of the wells with the microwell holder turned upside down and tapped vigorously three times in a row against absorbent paper to ensure complete removal of mixture from wells. The wells will be filled twice with 250 ul washing buffer and the mixture will be poured out and repeated twice. One hundred millilitre of substrate/chromogen will be added

to each well, mixed well by shaking the plate manually and incubated for 15 min at room temperature (20 – 25^oC) in the dark. One hundred millilitre of the stop solution will be added to each well, mixed gently by shaking the plates manually and absorbance measured within 30 min at 450 nm. The percentage absorbance will be calculated manually using the formula:

$$\frac{\text{Absorbance standard (of sample)}}{\text{Absorbance of zero standards}} \times 100 = \% \text{absorbance}$$

The zero standards were made equal to 100 % and the absorbance values will be quoted in percentage. The values calculated for the standard will be entered in a system of coordinates in a semi logarithmic graph paper against the aflatoxins concentration (ug/kg) in order to obtain the aflatoxin concentration in ug/kg actually contained in a sample, the concentration red from the calibration curve will be further multiplied by the dilution factor of 35 as obtained in the R-Bio pharm manual.

DATA ANALYSIS

Data generated will be used to describe *Aspergillus*/aflatoxins in kilishi. Summaries of data generated will be presented in tables and graphs using descriptive statistics.

Result of the Concentration of Total Aflatoxin in Kilishi Samples

Analysis of kilishi samples shows aflatoxin concentration values

3.3ppb, 0.033ppb, 0.6ppb, 0.8ppb, 1.6ppb, 1.5ppb, 1.2ppb, 0.9ppb, 0.96ppb, 0.4ppb, 1.4ppb, 1.6ppb, 1.5ppb, 2.5ppb, 1.9ppb, 2.1ppb, 2.0ppb, 1.1ppb, 3.0ppb, 0.3ppb, 3.8ppb, 0.8ppb, 0.7ppb, 0.95ppb, 3.2ppb, 0.7ppb, 1.5ppb, 3.6ppb, 2.7ppb, 0.85ppb, 0.85ppb, for Katsina state and 1.6ppb, 2.2ppb, 1.9ppb, 3.1ppb, 3.4ppb, 3.5ppb, 3.9ppb, 2.6ppb, 3.6ppb, 2.2ppb, 2.1ppb, 3.1ppb, 2.4ppb, 1.6ppb, 2.6ppb, 2.8ppb, 1.8ppb, 2.1ppb, 2.2ppb, 0.45ppb, 0.8ppb, 2.3ppb, 1.6ppb for Sokoto state.

Result of the Count on Mould Yeast for the Kilishi

The analysis of kilishi shows the mould/yeast count (CFU/g) as follows: 100, 80, 0,0, 10, 20, 50, 20, 0, 20, 20, 100, 10, 10,30,350, 20, 0, 30, 20, 0,10, 70, 20, 20, 70, 0,50, 50 for Katsina state and 30, 0, 0, 0,60, 0,20, 200, 0, 0,10, 0, 0, 0, 0,20, 00, 0, 0,0, 30 for Sokoto state.

Below is a descriptive statistics using bar chart showing the various occurrence of aflatoxin and mould/yeast in meat (kilishi) based on Local Government Area (LGA), colour of appearance and State.

Figure 1: The mean aflatoxin based on the colour of appearance of kilishi

Figure 2: The mean aflatoxin of kilishi based on Local Government Area

Figure 4: The mean aflatoxin of kilishi based on state

Figure 5: The mean coliforms based on appearance on the colour of kilishi

Figure 6: The mean yeast/mould based on appearance of the colour of kilishi

Figure 7: The mean total plate count based on appearance of the colour of kilishi

Figure 8: The mean coliforms of kilishi based on LGA

Figure 9: The mean yeast/mould in kilishi based on LGA

Figure 10: The mean total plate count of microbes in kilishi

Figure 11: The mean coliforms count of kilishi based on state

Figure 12: The mean yeast/mould count based on state

Figure 13: The mean total microbial plate count based on state

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

From fig 1 above the result of the physio-chemical analysis shows that the minimum mean occurrence of aflatoxin was 1.04ppb in light brown dried meat while the maximum mean was 3.6ppb in light reddish dried meat. This implies that going by EU standards of 4ppb for total aflatoxins; 2 ppb Afb1. Light reddish dried meat which is

about 27% of the mean of the sample based on the appearance is not fit for consumption.

From fig 2 above the result of the physio-chemical analysis shows that the minimum mean occurrence of aflatoxin was 1.33ppb in Katsina Local Government in Katsina state while the maximum mean was 3.18ppb in Denge Shuni Local Government Area. This implies that going by EU standards of 4ppb for total aflatoxins; 2 ppb

Afb1. Dried meat from Denge shuni LGA which is about 27% of the mean of the sample based on the LGA is not fit for consumption given the constituent of aflatoxin. Dried meat from Sokoto south is also above the acceptable limit of 2.0ppb. It's about 19.6% of the mean of the sample. From figure 4 above the result of the physio-chemical analysis shows that the minimum mean occurrence of aflatoxin was 1.5ppb in Katsina state while the maximum mean was 2.39ppb in Sokoto State. Dried meat from Sokoto is above the acceptable limit of 2.0ppb hence may not be completely fit for consumption.

From fig 5 above show the result of the microbiological analysis shows that the minimum mean occurrence of coliforms was 10fu/g in dark brown dried meat and light brown dried meat with fat respectively while the maximum mean was 27.08fu/g in reddish brown dried meat. From fig 6 above show the result of the microbiological analysis shows that the minimum mean occurrence of mould /yeast was 20fu/g in light brown dried meat with fat while the maximum mean was 166.5cfu/g in reddish brown dried meat. Dark brown dried meat had no occurrence of mould/yeast.

From fig 7 above show the result of the microbiological analysis shows that the minimum mean total plate count was 1000fu/g in light and reddish dried meat with fat while the maximum mean was 4853.33cfu/g in brown dried meat. From fig 8 above show the result of the microbiological analysis shows that the minimum mean Coliform was 15fu/g in Batagarawa, Katsina, Malumfashi LGAs respectively while the maximum mean was 60cfu/g in denge shuni.

From fig 9 above show the result of the microbiological analysis shows that the minimum mean yeast/mould was 20fu/g in Denge Shuni and Malumfashi LGAs respectively while the maximum mean was 90cfu/g in Katsina LGA. From fig 4 above show the result of the microbiological analysis shows that the minimum mean total plate counts 1906.67fu/g in Malumfashi LGA while the maximum mean was 4150cfu/g in Batagarawa LGA. Which is about 22.33% percent of the mean of sample. From fig 10 above show the result of the microbiological analysis shows that the minimum mean Colliforms was 15fu/g in Katsina State while the maximum mean was 36.93cfu/g in Sokoto which is about 71.11% percent of the mean of sample. Hence dried meat from Katsina is likely to be healthier for consumption.

From fig 12 above show the result of the microbiological analysis shows that the minimum mean mould/yeast was 61.67fu/g in Katsina State, while the maximum mean was 98.57cfu/g in Sokoto which is about 61.15% percent of the mean of sample. Hence dried meat from Katsina is likely to be healthier for consumption. From fig 13 above show the result of the microbiological analysis shows that the minimum mean mould/yeast was 61.67fu/g in Katsina state while the maximum mean was 98.57cfu/g in Sokoto which is about 57.5% percent of the mean of sample. Hence dried meat

from Katsina is likely to be healthier for consumption.

The results of the questionnaires administered have shown that out of a total sample size of 63 people, 27 (42.9%) respondents indicated that they have been involved in the production and marketing of Kilishi for 11 – 15 years. The results also show that as indicated by 50 respondents, the predominant type of meat used is cow meat. Furthermore, the results further revealed that the average shelf-life of the Kilishi products from 44 (69.8%) respondents is 1 – 5 days while 47 (74.6%) respondents identify Mycotoxin by a characteristic whitish appearance. On the basis of Mycotoxin knowledge and management, all the respondents indicated that they have heard of Mycotoxin but only 82.5% indicated that they are aware they can cause diseases. Additionally, 69.8% of the respondents refrigerate their Kilishi products in order to prevent mold while 28.6% have no inclination as to any method of preventing mold growth. A large proportion (87.3%) of the respondents do not notice mold growth in their products.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the present work indicated that the examined dried meats were contaminated with several moulds especially of the genus *Aspergillus*. Many of these moulds are capable of producing mycotoxin such as aflatoxins, ochratoxin and fumonisins. These findings indicate that there may be a risk of human exposure to mycotoxins through the consumption of the dried meat. Strict hygienic measures must be applied during the processing and storage of the meat samples and calls for concerted efforts on the part of relevant authorities to check the trend, since it is a public health challenge.

RECOMMENDATION

It is therefore recommended that a systematic method of production is designed in such a way that Kilishi producers are educated on the various critical control points in the system. Kilishi is a meat product and like other meat products it is subject to deterioration, therefore, the batch number, production date and expiry or best before date should be appended in every product sent to the market. Since the Kilishi is sold in open markets and in open stalls, it is possible that contamination will be increased therefore, this practice should be discouraged. The method of production should also be upgraded to a more mechanized form that will ensure hygienic preparations.

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